

ACUTE - Accessibility and Connectivity Knowledge Hub for Urban Transformation in Europe

WP3– Practitioner Interaction

D3.4.6 POLIS workshop

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Project Partners

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1 POLIS workshop on May 22nd 2024 in Utrecht

Seven practitioners from different cities (Utrecht, Stuttgart, Cork, Turkü, Lyon, Brussels) attended to the event. The aim of this workshop was to hear experiences of 15-min City and to identify opportunities and obstacles to implementing 15-Min City. To explore this second goal we used the methodology of the lego serious play with diverse questions around the concept.

Figure 1: POLIS workshop setting

Workshop – Part I : Building the components of a city of proximity model – 25 min

The participants individually build components that they see as part of a city of proximity using Lego models.

10 minutes were dedicated to individual construction. Participants share their stories and give meaning to the model they have built.

This time is followed by a pitch time, answering this question : *How is this component essential for a city of proximity?*

Workshop Part II : Creating a story: Sharing/exchanging – 25 min

Assembling and creating a City of proximity together.

Following the city of proximity components built by each participant, participants collectively created a city of proximity answering these different questions :

How can these components come together and be implemented in our cities?

Which components should be prioritized? Are there any missing? What goals can these components help reach?

Workshop part III : Discussion

This part was meant to disassemble the model and free exchanges about the city of proximity constructions.

Main outcomes

This workshop showed different stages of implementation of the concept and different preoccupations related to. For cities at latter stage of implementation 15-min City's business model question popped out. For cities at the earlier stage, the communication aspect of the concept and how-to positively impact mobility habits remains the principal questions.

During the discussion, a highlight in the importance of involving citizens at different steps and building the right communication emerged as the question to diversify the profile of citizens taking part of urban decisions.